

MOISTURE ABSORPTION OF GLUTEN POLYMERS AND FLAX/GLUTEN COMPOSITES

N. Vo Hong^{1*}, A.W. Van Vuure¹, P. Van Puyvelde², I. Verpoest¹

¹ Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, KU Leuven, Kasteelpark Arenberg 44, 3001 Heverlee, Belgium

² Department of Chemical Engineering, Soft Matter: Applied Rheology and Technology, KU Leuven, Willem de Croylaan 46, 3001 Heverlee, Belgium

* Corresponding author: Nhan.Vohong@mtm.kuleuven.be

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1. General introduction

As known for many decades, several environmental problems have been created due to the inability of natural organisms to degrade synthetic polymers. Considerable efforts have been made to develop biodegradable materials, especially interesting from renewable resources such as agricultural byproducts. Among candidate proteins, wheat gluten has received attention because it is a low-cost raw material, annually renewable, biodegradable and readily available.

Traditionally, wheat gluten is widely used for food applications such as breads, pasta, noodles, and cookies. Besides in food technology, the use of wheat gluten has been explored in non-food applications such as biopolymers and biocomposites [1-3]. In absence or at low concentrations of plasticizer, high-temperature compression molded wheat gluten powder upon cooling vitrifies into a rigid material. This rigid gluten biopolymer has also been combined with natural fibers to obtain green composites [4].

However, there are certain limitations for this type of composite, particularly regarding its processability and environmental (moisture) resistance. Gluten composites still contain a significant amount of water after processing. In the case of gluten polymers, the mechanical properties are affected considerably by the residual moisture

content [5]. Therefore, in case of gluten composites, their properties are also expected to change.

Humidity and its influence on fiber reinforced composites do not have to be considered so strongly in traditional carbon or glass fiber reinforced composites. However, it has a great influence on the properties of natural fiber composites. Because of the chemical constituents of fibers as well as biopolymer matrices, due to their hydrophilic nature there will always be a tendency to absorb moisture. This is a serious concern as there are potential outdoor applications, where moisture absorption will occur.

The interfacial bonds between the natural fibers and biopolymer matrices would be weakened with high water uptake [6]. The weakened interface causes the reduction of the mechanical properties of the composites. Indeed, modulus and strength decrease with immersion time [6-10]. However, there is little literature available about the influence of environmental humidity on the mechanical properties.

The aim of this research is to study the moisture absorption behaviour of gluten polymers and subsequently of flax fiber/gluten composites. Up till now, there have not been conclusive results on the effect of moisture content on the thermo-molded

gluten polymers, as well as on the rigid gluten composites.

2. Experiments

2.1. Materials

Wheat gluten powder sourced from Tereos Syral (Aalst, Belgium) contains 77.8% protein and typically 5.6% moisture content.

Hackled flax was delivered by Terre de Lin (France). This form of flax is a continuous ribbon, in which the fibers are well aligned. The linear density of this material is 30000 tex, and the preform has a width of about 25 cm.

2.2. Samples manufacturing

An extensive presentation of the procedure to make a prepreg from the fibres and gluten powder is given by Vo Hong et al. (2012) [4]. Briefly, the flax/gluten prepreps were prepared by spraying gluten powder on the wet fiber preforms till 33% in fiber volume fraction was obtained. The products were dried under vacuum at 20 °C to avoid any premature cross-linking of the gluten at higher temperature. At this dry state, the moisture content was measured according to AACC Approved method 44-15.02 [11]. Samples were dried for 24h at 130 °C until no further weight change was observed.

Subsequently, prepreps were immediately stored in the climate chamber at 50% RH and 20 °C for 7days for conditioning the moisture content. At this state, moisture content was determined again to see how much amount of water absorbed into the products. They were then stacked in unidirectional orientation at 8 layers and compression molded at 150 °C for 5 minutes and 5 bars in a hot pressing machine Zenith 2 (Pinette Emidecau Industries, Chalon sur Saône, France). As soon as they were taken out of the machine, their moisture content was determined again.

The same processing conditions were applied in the case of gluten polymers. After compression molding,

moisture content was measured and considered as the initial state for moisture absorption.

2.3. Moisture absorption and determination

After determining initial moisture content, the initial mass (M_{dry}) was recorded. All gluten polymer and composite samples were stored in a climate chamber at different RH's (50-80%) and 20 °C for moisture absorption. During storage time, samples were periodically withdrawn from the environment and immediately weighed (M_{wet}^t) using an electrical balance accurate to 0.0001g. The moisture absorption was monitored after 2 days and 7 days, and then plotted as the weight gain against the storage time. The weight gain (Eq 1.) due to moisture absorption was expressed as the increase in sample mass divided by its initial weight and multiplied by 100%. Thus,

$$\text{The weight gain} = \frac{M_{wet}^t - M_{dry}}{M_{dry}} * 100\% \quad (1)$$

Moisture absorption was determined in duplicate. After 2 and 7 days, the mechanical properties of the samples were immediately determined and then moisture content was measured.

2.4. Mechanical properties

In order to evaluate the mechanical behaviour of gluten polymers and composites after 2 and 7 days of moisture absorption, flexural tests were used. As soon as samples were withdrawn from the environment, they were tested on an Instron 4467 with a 1 kN load cell. The support length of the specimens was at least 16 times the thickness of the plates (± 2 mm), to obtain pure bending. The flexural modulus of each sample was determined by calculating the slope of the stress-strain curve in the initial linear region. At least three samples were tested in each configuration.

2.5. Glass transition temperature (T_g)

The glass transition temperature of gluten materials was determined as described by Jansens et al. (2012) [5]. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were used in a Q2000 DSC instrument (TA Instruments, New Castle, DE, USA)

using hermetically closed aluminum pans. At the beginning, samples were cooled down to -30 °C as a starting point. Afterwards, they were first heated from -30 °C to 110 °C at 10 °/min, kept at 110°C for 10 minutes, and then cooled down to -30 °C at the same rate. After equilibrating at -30 °C, they were heated a second time with the same rate as during the first heating. Based on two heating cycles, the T_g values are reported from the second heating run [12].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Moisture absorption and determination

The influence of moisture absorption on gluten polymers plays an important role as well on gluten composites. From Fig. 1, the absorption rate at 80% RH post storage of polymers is higher than at 50% RH. The same tendency is observed for composite samples. However, the absorption rate of composites is much faster than for polymers, particularly at 80% RH. Indeed, additional natural fibers in composites make the absorption more complex. Moisture can be absorbed through the fibers by capillarity and propagated through the matrix at the interface [13].

To investigate the moisture change after compression molding as function of post storage conditions, the moisture content of all gluten samples was measured (table 1). In earlier discussions [5], gluten polymers thermo-molded from gluten powder with 5.6% water content had a small increase in moisture content till 6.1% after compression molding. After post storage at 50% RH during 2 and 7 days, moisture content did not change significantly, whereas polymers absorbed more water after 80% RH post storage.

Opposite to pure polymers, gluten composites have some more significant changes in moisture content as function of storage conditions. Due to storing the dry prepregs at standard conditions of 50% RH and 20 °C, moisture content increases till 8.7% which is higher than in initial gluten powder. After compression molding, the moisture level in composites dramatically drops to 3.1%. At this dry state, materials seem to be anhydrous and start to

absorb moisture again. At 7 days at 50% RH, the moisture content of the composites is lower than the value of the polymers, but the absorption rate of the composites is faster than the polymers, showing that composites need less time to obtain the same moisture content as polymers. At 2 days and 80% RH, the same moisture content is observed for both gluten polymers and composites. However, composite samples absorb more water than polymers after 7 days at 80% RH. The fibres must be responsible for the faster absorption rate.

3.2. Mechanical properties

Moisture absorption has a negative effect on the mechanical properties of gluten materials (table 2). The higher post storage leads to lower mechanical properties. This effect on gluten polymers was discussed in the previous work of the authors [5]. The modulus was slightly lower and the strength was significantly reduced at longer storage time and in a higher humidity environment.

In the case of gluten composites, a clear difference in modulus is observed at different post storage conditions. Modulus decreases from 2 to 7 days at 50% RH as well as at 80% RH. Particularly, composite modulus dramatically decreases by 52% going from 50 to 80% RH after 7 days while polymer modulus dropped around 19%. In addition, the composite strength also reduces in higher humidity environment. It drops down till the strength values of polymers at 50% RH post storage. In the paragraph dealing with the correlation between mechanical properties and moisture content, this will be further discussed. Note that the composite modulus represents the fiber straightness and homogeneities of fiber and matrix distribution, whereas the composite strength also shows the quality of the interfacial adhesion between fibers and matrix. Both the modulus and strength in this study showed quite low values compared to theoretical calculations (Rule of Mixtures) [4] indicating the impregnation of gluten in between fiber bundles was not optimized yet.

3.3. Glass transition temperature

The Tg values of gluten materials are also presented in table 2. It was shown that the Tg decreased by exposing gluten polymers in high humid environment [5]. This could be explained by plasticization of the gluten by water [14]. When added to polymeric materials, a plasticizer modifies their three-dimensional organization, decreasing attractive intermolecular forces and increasing free volume and chain mobility [2]. The same phenomenon is observed in gluten composites. The Tg of composite samples reduces dramatically compared with polymer samples at every post storage condition. In the next paragraphs, the Tg as function of moisture content will be discussed.

3.4. Relationship between mechanical properties and moisture content

The correlation between modulus of gluten materials and moisture content at different post storage conditions is shown in Fig. 2. The polymer modulus is fairly low when increasing moisture content. However, the studied range of moisture contents was relatively small, so it did not heavily affect the modulus [5]. At higher moisture level, the modulus significantly drops as e.g. reported by Woerdeman et al. (2004) [1]. For the case of gluten composites, the influence of moisture content is entirely clear. The moduli drop steadily at higher moisture content ($R^2 = 0.93$).

Fig. 3 shows the strength as function of moisture content for all gluten materials. A decrease in strength corresponds to an increase in moisture content. The strength is linear correlated with moisture content for polymers ($R^2 = 0.91$) and composites ($R^2 = 0.93$).

3.5. Relationship between glass transition temperature and moisture content

Fig. 4 plots the correlation between Tg and moisture content for all gluten materials. Moisture content shows a linear correlation with Tg for polymer samples ($R^2 = 0.98$) and composite samples ($R^2 = 0.82$). Tg reduces with increasing moisture content.

The Tg of composite samples shows lower values than for polymer samples at the same level of moisture content. This could be explained by higher amount of moisture in the polymer matrix of composites. This type of composite includes two components which have ability to absorb water. Flax fibers are known for the hydrophilic character of cellulose. It is possible that the flax fibres would conduct moisture into the gluten matrix. As a result, apparently the moisture content in the matrix of the composites is higher than in gluten polymers at the same global moisture content. Therefore, the Tg of gluten composites would be lower than in gluten polymers at the same global level of moisture. More work is needed to elucidate the exact mechanism.

4. Conclusion

The effect of moisture absorption on gluten polymers and composites has been studied. It shows that gluten materials absorb more moisture in higher humidity environment. Moreover, the mechanical properties are linearly correlated with moisture content. The decrease in modulus and strength corresponds to the increase in moisture content. Finally, the glass transition temperature is also strongly affected by the level of moisture. The glass transition temperatures of gluten composites are lower than in the gluten polymer at the same global moisture content.

Fig. 1. Different levels of moisture absorption of gluten materials at 50 and 80% RH after 7 days.

Table 1. Moisture content of gluten materials after compression molding and at different post storage conditions.

Samples	Moisture content (%)
Gluten polymers after compression molding	6.1 (0.1)
Gluten polymers at 2days, 50% RH*	5.9 (0.0)
Gluten polymers at 7days, 50% RH*	6.0 (0.1)
Gluten polymers at 2days, 80% RH*	7.2 (0.0)
Gluten polymers at 7days, 80% RH*	8.1 (0.0)
Dry prepreps	1.4 (0.2)
Prepreps at 7days, 50% RH	8.7 (0.2)
Gluten composites after compression molding	3.1 (0.1)
Gluten composites at 2days, 50% RH	4.7 (0.1)
Gluten composites at 7days, 50% RH	5.5 (0.2)
Gluten composites at 2days, 80% RH	7.5 (0.6)
Gluten composites at 7days, 80% RH	10.0 (0.1)

* Data is taken from earlier work of the authors [5]. Standard deviation is given in brackets.

Table 2. Mechanical properties and glass transition temperature of gluten materials at different post storage conditions.

Samples	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Tg (°C)
Gluten polymers at 2days, 50% RH*	4.2 (0.2)	47.6 (2.9)	76.5 (0.2)
Gluten polymers at 7days, 50% RH*	4.3 (0.2)	43.3 (1.4)	76.7 (0.4)
Gluten polymers at 2days, 80% RH*	3.6 (0.2)	34.8 (3.3)	71.5 (1.1)
Gluten polymers at 7days, 80% RH*	3.5 (0.1)	32.6 (2.3)	65.0 (1.3)
Gluten composites at 2days, 50% RH	12.9 (0.6)	58.6 (5.0)	56.6 (0.3)
Gluten composites at 7days, 50% RH	10.4 (1.0)	59.8 (8.6)	57.3 (1.3)
Gluten composites at 2days, 80% RH	6.7 (0.1)	54.1 (6.0)	47.7 (2.9)
Gluten composites at 7days, 80% RH	4.9 (0.4)	42.9 (5.7)	44.0 (1.0)

* Data is taken from earlier work of the authors [5]. Standard deviation is given in brackets.

Fig. 2. Modulus of gluten materials as function of moisture content at different post storage conditions.

Fig 3. Strength of gluten materials as function of moisture content at different post storage conditions.

Fig 4. Glass transition temperature of gluten materials as function of moisture content at different post storage conditions.

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